

Cadmium sulfide doped with silver as CO₂ gas sensor using pyrolysis technique

Uday Ali Sabeeh Al-Jarah¹, Haidar Jawad Mohamad², Yahya Mustafa Abdul-Hussein³

¹Department of Science, College of Basic Education, University of Misan, Misan, Iraq

²Department of Physics, College of Science, Mustansiriyah University, Baghdad, Iraq

³Directorate of Materials Research, Ministry of Science and Technology, Baghdad, Iraq

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ABSTRACT

The monitoring of CO₂ in our life safety, industrial, and chemical laboratory applications make it an inspiring task. The chemical spray pyrolysis technique was used to prepare CdS/Ag thin films. The nanocrystalline cadmium sulfide thin films were doped with Silver at different doping concentrations (0%, 2%, and 4%). The morphologies, structures, and gas sensing properties of CdS/Ag films are presented. The samples were characterized using X-ray diffraction (XRD) and atomic force microscope (AFM). The XRD results show that the films are a polycrystalline composition and hexagonal type with a favoured orientation along (111) direction. The average grain size (nm) of AFM is between 75 and 55 nm. As a result, Ag doping changes the sensitivity of the samples respectively with the percentage of doping with time. The synthesis samples show controlling sensitivity and the small response of sensitivity are the key point in this study.

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Corresponding Author:

Haidar Jawad Mohamad

Department of Physics, College of Science, Mustansiriyah University

Falastin St, Baghdad, Iraq

Email: haidar.mohamad@uomustansiriyah.edu.iq

1. INTRODUCTION

Cadmium sulfide (CdS) belong to the II-VI group and considered popular material for a variety of devices. It has an average bandgap of 2.42 eV. For a heterojunction solar cell, used as the appropriate material as a window material. It has a high absorption coefficient, good transfer efficiency, reliable, and inexpensive [1]. CdS considered as interesting material because it used at different applications for instance diode sensor [2], transistor [3], photosensor [4], photodetectors [5], photodiodes [6]. CdS have been deposited by chemical bath deposition (CBD) method [7], sol-gel [8], pulsed laser deposition technique (PLD) [9], chemical vapour deposition (CVD) [10], RF-sputtering [11]. Spray pyrolysis offers certain benefits over the other techniques when compared to them. It has a flexible process mechanism, can create large-area and nanostructured films, and has a low-cost yet effective method. Therefore, it is used to fabricate the samples within this work.

The nanomaterial sensors have been introduced based on multiple principles of absorption for the ultraviolet-infrared (UV-IR) range [12], [13], the resistance of electric circuit [14]–[16], amperometry [17]. Current sensing techniques have been proven to improve in order to test the effectiveness, stability, reaction time, and sensitivity when nanomaterials are used. Organic, inorganic or hybrid components are used in sensing applications. Organic materials have several desired characteristics such as mass transfer, surface chemistry, and gas conductivity. However, inorganic nanomaterials are better in terms of their physical stability, resistivity, and optical characteristics [18], while hybrid nanomaterials combine between the organic and inorganic materials which improve the functional details [19].

In order to track and regulate indoor air quality, carbon dioxide (CO₂) detectors are essential [20]. Ecological, industrial, and sensors are all interested in CO₂ sensing using cheap, remotely controlled, extremely important sensors that operate at ambient temperature [21]. Because of the immense effect of CO₂ pollution on climate change, CO₂ tracking is important in the area of sensing applications [22]. CO₂ detectors are also essential in the agriculture sector [23], as well as breathing monitoring systems in medicine [24], [25], atmospheric institutes in nanotechnology [26], and petroleum refineries [27]. In addition, CO₂ sensors are in high demand for space and industrial uses, such as moderate fire alarm that detects chemical compounds suggestive of a fire [28]. Despite this, owing to the increase chemical stability of CO₂, there are about a few experiments in CO₂ detectors that can function at ambient temperature. In contrast to spectrometric CO₂ gas detectors, physical CO₂ gas sensors based on metal oxides have a low power consumption, convenience, and small size [29]. Gas sensors based on TiO₂ nanostructured has been introduced [30]. Gas sensing technology can be found in two leading commercial platforms: electronic (lambda sensors) and optical (nondispersive infrared (NDIR) sensors and optrodes) [31]

Danie *et al.* [32] synthesised a CdS/WO_x nanocomposite that exhibits photocapacitive solar energy storage. They performed spectroscopy characterization and temporary photocurrent reaction comparative to an effect attributed to the extinction of electron-hole reconnected in CdS due to hole transmission across the work sheds light on how the constituent materials could be used in the future self-charging solar device. Aishwarya *et. al* synthesized CdS nanoparticles under different concentrations of cadmium chloride and sodium sulphide used for applications in cancer therapy [33]. Under various doses of cadmium chloride and sodium sulfide, escherichia coli cells were utilized to produce CdS nanoparticles. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was used to examine the morphology of the nanoparticles, and X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) was utilized to examine the elemental composition of the nanoparticles. The functional groups of the nanoparticles were determined using Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy. X-ray diffraction was used to determine the crystalline nature of nanoparticles. Foodborne pathogens were used to test the antibacterial properties of CdS nanoparticles. Zahra *et al.* [34] synthesized cadmium sulfide as quantum dots which have unique medical applications contains identifying cells, identifying viruses, and imaging intercellular proceedings.

This work is dedicated to fabricating CdS samples with Ag doping percentage (0%, 2%, and 4%). The method of the fabrication is Pyrolysis technique. The morphological, structural, and sensitivity towards CO₂ are presented. The homemade device was used to measure the sensitivity of the CO₂ for the three samples with the response time. The response time is very short compared to other works which open door for many applications. As a result, much effort has done into finding or developing new CO₂ sensitive mixtures that can operate at ambient temperature and provide particularly, ambient environment activities, fast response, and a rapid and reusable reaction.

2. PROPOSED METHOD

The CdS thin films were fabricated from a 0.1 M water solution of Cadmium Sulfide CdSO₄.8H₂O, by spray pyrolysis technique, onto a glass substrate. The silver (Ag) doping silver nitrate (AgNO₃) powder dissolved in a precursor solution of CdSO₄ with different weight percentages (W.%). The Ag-doped specimens fabricated with the different ratios of 0, 2, and 4 W.% silver concentrations. The CdS specimens fabricated with the same settings, of solution volume 100 ml and nozzle, to the resulting solution sprayed on preheated glass. The chemical equations can be describing the prepared samples as (1), (2).

After that, the CdS layer added to the CdS samples that resulted from (1) to have the doped samples as (3).

The deposition parameters applied to the preparation of CdS thin films are present in Table 1.

Table 1. Deposition parameters applied in this research

Item	Details
CdSO ₄ .8H ₂ O solution concentration	0.1M
Gas pressure	1 bar
Substrate temperature (C _o)	350 C _o
Nozzle to substrate distance	25 cm
Solvent	Distilled water
Deposition of one time	10 Sec
Deposition total time (minutes)	15 min
Rat of spray	2.5 ml/ min
Spray time during each cycle	50 Sec

3. METHOD

The sensor element was linked in series with millimetre electrical impedance tests were done using two millimetres for current, external voltage measurements, and power source in the range of (0-20) Volt to examine the electrical characteristics of the examined specimens. Gas sensing tests carried out using a home-built gas sensing chamber (gas flow elements) as shown in Figure 1. Test chamber unit consists of a stainless steel almost cylindrical shape with diameter and height 20 cm and 16 cm respectively. The base has removable O – ring sealed. The chamber volume is 5024 cm³ with 50 mbar pressure. The device located at ministry of science and technology. Where CO₂ gas preparation by the (4).

The film surface adsorbed CO₂ gas which causes increasing the total resistance of the sample. It is promising to reduce the required effective temperature by reducing the heating power and improve the sensor productivity reaction. The nanoscale layer changes the surface exhaustion and can lead to a different reaction with the nanostructure. The increase of crystalline size increased boundary resistance, indicating that the roughness average contributes to gas sensitivity. This lead to a change in the response of the sensitivity of the doped sample. The literature shows that resistance of the detector at RT amplified or reduced because of the electrolytic separation of the tested gasses in the exterior sample [35]. Because Cd atoms occupy the majority of the tetrahedral sites and there are vacant sites, the specimen structure is rather open. As a result, CdS has plenty of places to tolerate inherent defects and immutable doping. The gas sensitivity of thin film elements for CO₂ gas was evaluated at room temperature.

For lowering and oxidizing gases, the resistance reaction of each sensor structure was converted into a sensitivity value using the frequently used formula 5 [36].

$$S = \Delta R/R$$

$$S = \frac{R_{\text{air}} - R_{\text{gas}}}{R_{\text{air}}} \quad (5)$$

where S is the sensitivity, R_{air} is the resistance in air and R_{gas} resistance with gas. Figure 1 shows the setup of the suggested system in the lab.

Figure 1. The setup of homemade gas sensing measurement

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, it is explained the results of research and at the same time is given the comprehensive discussion. The results divided into three sections regarding to cover the details and data of the suggested samples. These sections are morphological, structural, and sensing properties.

4.1. Morphological properties

The morphology of the deposited films examined using an atomic force microscope (AFM) (Angstrom AA3000). Characteristic 3D and 2D AFM pictures of the CdS: Ag specimen synthesized at different doping concentrations (pure (0%), 2%, and 4%) are shown in Figure 2. Figure 2(a) has homogenous structure surface because it is pure without any adding materials. While Figures 2(b) and 2(c) has different surface morphology because of the metallic Ag.

Figure 2. 3D and 2D of AFM images of (a) pure (0%), (b) 2%, and (c) 4% Ag-doped CdS films

Table 2 shows the average crystal size, average roughness, and root mean square (RMS) roughness as determined by AFM. The crystallite size and RMS roughness of the film have risen as the doping concentration has grown. Columnar grain development in the structure might be causing the crystallite size to rise. The crystalline size findings acquired by AFM research differ from those obtained from X-ray diffraction (XRD) observations using the Scherrer equation [37]. This due to that AFM results were described exterior crystalline surface but the XRD results were described interior crystalline structure, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Structural characteristics of CdS: Ag specimen

Doping Concentration	RMS (nm)	Average grain size (nm) of AFM	Max crystalline size (nm) of XRD	Roughness average (nm)
pure	81.822	75	27.7	62.716
2%	131.893	65	37.5	100.479
4%	150.547	55	53.3	117.626

4.2. Structural properties

Structural details of the CdS/Ag samples presented by XRD technique of Shimadza-6000 using Cu K α radiation. Figure 3 shows the XRD data of pure and CdS doped with Ag thin film. These samples show polycrystalline and peaks that are ascribed to the hexagonal structure. The peaks of the film corresponding to Miller planes (111) and (102) reflections position at $2\theta=26.6$ and $2\theta=36.7$ with ($x=0, 2\%$ and 4%) respectively, for the pure and doping samples. The CdS structure films reported by many studies confirming the cubic and hexagonal crystalline shape [38].

There are no peaks associated to metallic Ag or Ag compounds. As a result, Ag atoms can be exchanged for sulphite atoms or integrated into the CdS lattice's interstitial sites. This indicates that the precursors have been fully converted to the CdS phase, and that Ag doping has had no effect on the CdS lattice's hexagonal structure. Despite the variations in the atomic radius of the server and the dopant, there are no changes in the peak position.

4.3. Sensing properties

The sensitivity response time is changed with the doping ratio 4%, which means we can control the sensitivity time. The previous reports show long sensitivity response time for CdS [35]. However, the sensitivity percentage is changed with changing the doping ratio. The lowest sensitivity (%) with the doping ratio 4% due to the effect of the Ag. The high interaction to CO $_2$ can be explain to the sample modification. In the two-dimensional system, the electron-electron interaction in the presence of periodically heightened disorders can establish the adsorption, ionization, and diffusion interaction resulting in different sensitivity.

There are two significant indicators for the time response and recovery curve to show sensor performance. The response time or the raising time describe the sensor resistance that reach 90% from the steady point, while the recovery or falling time describes the sensor resistance to recover about 90% from the total changing after test gas stopped pumping. The faster response and recovery sample time of the sensor is due to adsorption at the sample surface. The small response time means that sample has fast oxidization with gas. The sensitivity CdS:Ag thin films (0%, 2% and 4%) shown in Figure 4.

Figure 3. XRD data of pure, 2%, and 4% Ag-doped CdS films

Figure 4. The relation between the sensitivity and time in second

5. CONCLUSION

Pure and Ag-doped CdS specimens were deposited using the chemical spray pyrolysis technique. The size of the molecular of the doped samples is larger than that of the pure sample. In this research, we found CdS has a polycrystalline composition with Hexagonal type, and has favourite directions for the growth of granule (111) and (102). We observed the sensitivity was decreased with an increased doping ratio because Silver is oxidized before the formation of a crystalline compound. We observed the sensitivity was very low

because the CO₂ gas was inert gas. The roughness was increased with doping increased too. The response time is very short comparing with other studies which make these samples are desirable to detect CO₂.

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BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Dr. Uday Ali Sabeeh Al-Jarah received the B.Sc. degree in physics science from Mustansiriyah University, Iraq (1998), the M.Sc. degree in Physics from Mustansiriyah University, Iraq (2003), and the Ph.D. degree in Physics from University of Exeter, U.K., (2013). He is a Senior Lecturer, and the Head of the Renewable Energy Committee at the University of Misan since 2016. He has authored or coauthored more than 7 publications, with 3 H-index. His research interests include spectroscopy, Nano-optics, ultrafast magnetic phenomena, and laser applications. He can be contacted at email: drudayaaljarah@uomisan.edu.iq.

Dr. Haidar Jawad Mohamad received the B.Sc. degree in physics science from the Mustansiriyah University, Iraq, the M.Sc. degree in Physics from Mustansiriyah University, Iraq, and the Ph.D. degree in Physics from The University of Exeter, U.K., 2015. He used to hold several administrative positions with the department of physics, Mustansiriyah University from 2016 to 2018, including administrator of Postgraduate students. He is currently Assis. Professor with the Department of Physics, Mustansiriyah University. He has supervised and co-supervised more than 4 masters and 1 Ph.D. students. He has authored or coauthored more than 35 publications, with 3 H-index. His research interests include soft computing, machine learning, intelligent systems and optics. He can be contacted at email: haidar.mohamad@uomustansiriyah.edu.iq.

Yahya Mustafa Abdul-Hussein received the B.Sc. degree in physics science from the Mustansiriyah University, Iraq, M.Sc. degree in Republic of India, University of acharya, Nagarjuna university of Science college, Department of Physics, 2016. employee at ministry of science and technology. He can be contacted at email: yahyamus1975@gmail.com.